

PRISMA overview scenario protocol

The full cost of rolling back ambition

Asymmetric net-zero transitions in a disrupted and uncertain climate regime

For inquiries about the protocol and expressing interest in participation, please contact scenarios@net0prisma.eu

Narrative

The unprecedented weakening of multilateral climate action, exemplified by the US withdrawal from the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement, as well as the rollback of national policies and threats to pillars of decarbonization such as the EU ETS, is creating profound uncertainties about the capacity to implement regional decarbonization strategies. Though these rollbacks might be temporary, some institutional changes are likely to lead to a protracted weakening of climate ambition, possibly followed by a sudden revitalisation of climate policies in pursuit of climate stabilization. Despite such a politically volatile context, some decarbonization strategies, in particular renewables, electricity storage and end-use electrification, continue to advance given their advantageous economics, but in a regionally differentiated way which reflects political priorities and fossil fuel endowments.

The main goal of the PRISMA scenario protocol is to analyse the implications of regionally differentiated roll-backs on the ambition of net-zero climate strategies and to quantify the climate and economic consequences of disrupted decarbonization plans and the costs of making up the lost time. The regional differentiation is driven not by ethical or responsibility principles, but by the political economy of the decarbonization transition exemplified by the division between electro and petro-states. Thanks to the falling cost of low-carbon strategies and the efficiency gains of electrification, countries with limited fossil resources or clean technology industrial ambition might keep up -even if partly- with the proposed ambition, whereas fossil-endowed regions and those under their geopolitical influence roll back legislation more forcefully. This narrative embeds generalized headwinds on climate action, but maintains the observed momentum of clean energy technologies resulting from economic, competitiveness, and security reasons. Short-term pathways reflect diverging trends of technological development (e.g. fast for RES and electricity, slow or null for CCS). CO₂ removal is

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very limited in the short to medium term as it does not align with an industrial strategy, but can pick up after net zero in the latter part of the century.

We also explore what happens if the climate mitigation ambition resurfaces after a prolonged delay, with countries rushing to make up for lost time and incurring costs depending on the extent of their rollback. This allows quantifying the regional costs of delaying action in a fragmented policy regime. Finally, we aim to quantify the extent to which a partial mitigation approach focused on three key climate transition pillars - RES deployment, electricity storage and final energy electrification, whose momentum is expected to continue for reasons beyond emission cuts- can help fill the ambition gap of the fragmented scenarios in the near term.

High level scenario description

To implement the above narrative, we foresee 4 main scenarios:

- 1. Meet Aspirations**
- 2. Asymmetric Roll-Back**
- 3. Late Reawakening**
- 4. Staying Alive**

1. Meet Aspirations

All countries implement the current policies, the NDCs to 2030 (and where available 2035), and the existing LTS. This is a standard scenario where countries meet their long-term stated aspirations, with regionally differentiated efforts and no explicit mechanisms for international coordination (e.g. Article 6). Except, in this scenario, the USA will target net-zero emission in 2050.

For countries without LTS targets, we use the assumptions of the ELEVATE project: an exogenous carbon tax trajectory based on near term policies, which follows either NDC implied carbon price, growing at a region specific rate with a lower bound or carbon tax path implied by current policy, whichever is higher. The main goal of these assumptions is to ensure policy continuity while maintaining a gradually increasing mitigation incentive whenever long-term net-zero commitments are absent.

2. Asymmetric Roll-Back

In this scenario, the climate mitigation aspirations of scenario “Meet Aspirations” are rolled back across all countries, though in differentiated ways across regions. Specifically, the key climate signposts (e.g. NDCs, LTS targets) are moved forward in

time by 10, 20 or 30 years depending on the region. As detailed below, we assign countries to 3 clusters, as in Appendix 1.

3. Late Reawakening

This scenario follows “Asymmetric Roll-Back” and from a prespecified date (see below for details) it goes back to “Meet Aspirations”, specifically tries to meet the regional LTS targets of scenario “Meet Aspirations” (starting from the regionally differentiated roll-backs). It is essential to monitor infeasibilities and address them in the analysis.

4. Staying Alive (or Low Regrets)

This scenario follows “Asymmetric Roll-Back” in terms of reduced ambition, but quantifies whether no/low-regret transition strategies in the short term can help fill the ambition gap. In particular, investments (or capacity) in renewables, electricity storage, and end-use electrification are maintained at the same level as those in scenario #1.

Research questions

RQ1 (comparing scenario 2 and 1): What are the implications of regionally differentiated rollbacks of mitigation ambition for:

- Climate change
- Emissions, e.g. regional NZ year
- Investments
- Technological innovation
- Energy costs
- Energy security
- Climate impacts (post process)

RQ2 (comparing scenario 3 and 1): Is it feasible to make up the lost time and what are the costs, for each region, in terms of:

- Policy costs
- Shadow carbon prices
- Energy prices
- Energy security

Also, show how the extent of roll back influences the costs of regaining climate momentum.

RQ3 (comparing scenario 4 and 2): Can a focus on sectoral strategies which have the strongest economic and efficiency rationale -namely RES deployment and

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electrification of end uses- reduce the costs of rollback, in terms of closing the mitigation gap with respect to scenario 1, and if so till when and in which regions?

Scenario implementation detail

In all scenarios modeling teams should implement the Current Policies. Current policies refer to those implemented by governments across countries at present or targets that are non-binding and backed by effective policy instruments.

The climate policies that have to be defined within the scenario “Meet Aspirations” are NDCs and LTSs, whereas Current Policies follow the latest update from the ELEVATE project.

- NDC: Nationally Determined Contributions

NDCs represent the climate commitments that countries have formally submitted under the Paris Agreement, representing the near-term policy ambition that governments have pledged to implement through 2030 and more recently in 2035 (not all countries have submitted their NDC for 2035 yet).

- LTS: Long-Term Strategies

LTSs are mid-century decarbonization strategies that countries are encouraged to develop under Article 4.19 of the Paris Agreement, and they represent long-term ambition. They are usually translated into the models with a pledged Net Zero year.

Asymmetric Roll-Back (scenario #2):

The rollback is motivated by two main factors: 1. A general loss of momentum of climate change as a political priority given the crisis of multilateral climate action and 2. The geopolitics of the climate transition, with two conflicting strategies between petro and electro-states, and the influence they exert on other, smaller, economies.

To capture factor 1, we will apply a reduced effort compared to the stated ambition to all countries. However, the extent of reduction varies across countries. To characterise the extent of regional rollback, we cluster countries to 3 groups depending on their fossil endowments and the extent to which a switch to clean energy is ongoing. Details

on the classification and the exact country mapping is provided in *Appendix 1: regional classification*.

To implement reduced aspirations (scenario #2), delaying climate targets, e.g. move all milestones targets like NDCs for 2030 and 2035, and Long Term Strategies by 10, 20, and 30 years depending on the cluster. Climate milestone targets are delayed by 10 years for *transition leaders*, 20 for *diversifying economies*, and by 30 for *fossil-dependent economies*. In addition to the forward shifting of the LTS target, we also envision a weakening of the capacity to reach net-zero CO₂, due to the higher costs of the last decarbonization steps. As a result, for countries having net-zero targets in their LTS, in scenario #2 those are weakened to 80% of the target (e.g. 20% residual emissions from current levels)

Late Reawakening (scenario #3)

For the scenario with late awakening (#3), follow the scenario #2 “Asymmetric Roll-Back” till 2035. From 2040 onwards, the model is free to resume LTS targets (for dynamic models this means investments are already free in 2035, which allow 2040 stocks to differ); for some countries, this will result in infeasibilities. If that happens, keep track of that, and move the LTS target by 5-year periods until a feasible solution is found.

Staying Alive (scenario #4)

For scenario #4, follow scenario #2 but on top add low-regret investments and strategies. In particular, fix the investments or capacity of renewables, storage, grid and electrification rates to those of scenario #1, throughout the entire century. The objective is to test whether maintaining early investments in mature low-carbon technologies can reduce long-term adjustment costs and avoid lock-in effects, even under weaker or delayed climate ambition.

Forward-looking models

For perfect foresight models, in scenarios #2, 3, 4 please fix investments at the respective values depending on the scenario.

Post Net-Zero

When a country/region reaches net-zero (in the scenarios where this happens), modelers are free to set the post net-zero path either at net-zero emissions or also allow emission to become net negative. However, CDR should be kept at realistic levels within the model assumptions, avoiding very large Co₂ removals globally. For the

specific implementation of post net zero (e.g. choice of carbon price schedule), models are free to choose their preferred way.

Land use and Non-CO2 gases

Land use CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions are priced at equivalent levels to the industrial CO₂ emissions. Land-use non-CO₂ emissions are capped at 300 USD/tCO₂ (2010 USD) to avoid unrealistically high values.

Choice of SSP

We leave freedom to models to choose the underlying SSP between SSP2 and SSP3. From a narrative standpoint, SSP3 best matches this design, but we understand the difficulties for the team to implement it. For each of the 4 core scenarios, we provide scenario naming for both SSP2 and SSP3. Teams can decide whether to provide both of them (encouraged) or focus on one at their discretion. SSP2 is mandatory for comparability but we highly encourage teams also to submit SSP3 results.

Expectations on outcomes

As common in recent policy-focused model comparison, the wedge between scenarios has become smaller over time given the rising role of clean technologies for non-climate reasons. Nonetheless we expect scenarios to be sufficiently spaced in order to be able to tell them apart within the model variability. Here are some rough result expectations, based on a first-cut implementation with the WITCH model:

- Emission peak year: 2030 for scenario#1, ≥ 2040 for scenario #2, 2035-40 for scenario #3 and #4
- Temperature gap between scenario #1 and #2 $\geq 1/2^\circ\text{C}$
- 2100 Temperature of scenario #2 $> 2^\circ\text{C}$ (see for example the outcomes of the WITCH preliminary runs in the chart)

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Scenario matrix summary:

We have 4 core scenarios, with two underlying SSPs at choice (e.g. 4 to 8 scenarios depending on capacity to implement both SSPs). There is one variant for WP3. For WP2, the core scenarios are sufficient.

	Details	Scenario Names
1 .Meet Aspirations	All countries implement current policies, NDCs (2030/2035), and Long-Term Strategies (LTS). Climate ambition follows stated national commitments, with carbon prices reflecting near-term policies and gradually increasing mitigation incentives.	SSP2 - Meet Aspirations SSP3 - Meet Aspirations
2. Asymmetric Roll-Back	Climate ambition is rolled back across all countries in differentiated ways. NDC and LTS milestones are delayed by 10 years for transition leaders, 20 for diversifying economies, and by 30 for fossil-dependent economies and net-zero ambitions are weakened.	SSP2 - Asymmetric Roll-Back SSP3 - Asymmetric Roll-Back
3. Late Reawakening	Countries initially follow the rollback pathway, then resume LTS targets after a delay (around 2035-2040). Regions attempt to return to original climate objectives, requiring accelerated mitigation and possible adjustment of targets for feasibility.	SSP2 - Late Reawakening SSP3 - Late Reawakening

<p>4. Staying Alive</p>	<p>Same policy ambition as the rollback scenario, but investments in renewables, electricity storage, grid expansion, and end-use electrification remain at levels of the ambition scenario to test low-regret transition strategies.</p>	<p>SSP2 - Staying Alive SSP3 - Staying Alive</p>
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Notes:

- For all scenarios, it's mandatory to run SSP2. It's optional but recommended to provide the results also for SSP3.

Appendix 1: regional classification

We use indicators on fossil fuel wealth (from the WB wealth of nations, to capture the fossil assets of each country), of RES growth in the past decade (to capture which countries are investing in clean energy), of GHG intensity of the economy (to capture structural economic factors).

Plotting these variables provides a first cut mapping of countries in this space. The chart highlights a negative correlation between fossil fuel assets and growth in renewable energy, further reinforced by the GHG intensity of the economies (bubble sizes). The plot already highlights geographical patterns, e.g. with resource poor, high renewable energy growth and low emission intensity areas such as Europe and Japan/South Korea, while Middle East countries sit at the other end of the spectrum. Major economies such as the US, China and India appear to be middle ground.

From this, we can classify countries based on these indicators, testing K-Means, Hierarchical Clustering and Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) clustering methods. Using 3 clusters for interpretability (though the data suggests even 4 or 5 clusters could be viable), results in the following example (GMM cluster), which identifies Fossil-dependent economies (e.g. Economies with high fossil fuel rents, high GHG intensity, and limited RES growth), Diversifying economies (Moderate fossil dependence,

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improving renewables growth, but still carbon-intensive production) and Transition leaders (Low fossil fuel rents, high renewable energy growth, and low GHG intensity). Some countries are missing for missing data (to be fixed)

Additional dimensions can be considered, even qualitatively; for example Japan and South Korea are classified as green in this method, but they are under the strong economic and political influence of the US, and as a result they would probably need to be moved to a less proactive cluster. On the other hand, China is heavily invested in the green transition, having become the key manufacturer of clean energy technologies and exerting influence in many countries with significant FDI investments. However, this classification provides a reasonable and data-driven approach that we can use for our scenarios.

Country Clusters Based on Fossil Dependence, Renewable Growth, and GHG Intensity

Please see detailed mapping of countries to clustered regions in the tab ‘NET-Zero data’ in the attached spreadsheet “PRISMA_WP6_Scenario_Protocol.xlsx”

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